

A FRAMEWORK TO STANDARDIZE GAIT STUDY PROTOCOLS IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE

*SOP for REDCap users: Import data dictionary & how
to use it as basis for your project*

Import Data Dictionary

To import a data dictionary file into redcap, you can do the following:

1. go to the project setup tab for the project you want to import the structure into
2. select the data dictionary tab

The screenshot shows the REDCap Project Setup interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with the following sections:

- Project Home and Design**: Project Home (circled in red), Project Setup, Designer, Dictionary, Codebook. Project status: Development.
- Data Collection**: Record Status Dashboard, Add / Edit Records, Show data collection instruments.
- Applications**: Project Dashboards, Data Exports, Reports, and Stats, Field Comment Log, PRODUCTION CHANGES, E-CONSENT REQUIREMENTS, REDCap Wiki.
- External Modules**: Manage, View Logs.
- Help & Information**: Help & FAQ, Video Tutorials, Suggest a New Feature, Contact REDCap administrator.

The main content area shows the 'Project Setup' tab (circled in red and labeled with a red '1'). The project status is 'Development' and 'Completed steps 0 of 7'. The 'Main project settings' section includes options for surveys and longitudinal data collection. The 'Design your data collection instruments' section has a 'Data Dictionary' link (circled in red and labeled with a red '2'). Below this are sections for 'Enable optional modules and customizations', 'Set up project bookmarks (optional)', and 'User Rights and Permissions'.

Import Data Dictionary

To import a data dictionary file into redcap, you can do the following:

1. go to the project setup tab for the project you want to import the structure into
2. select the data dictionary tab
3. select chose file under the title "Upload your Data Dictionary file:"
4. find the location of your data dictionary file, which should be a *.csv file
5. select the data dictionary file you want to import (*GaitDataDictionary_v1.csv*)

The screenshot shows the REDCap interface for uploading a Data Dictionary. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Project Home, Project Setup, Online Designer, Data Dictionary, and Codebook. Below the tabs, there is a video link: VIDEO: How to use this page. The main text explains that the module is used for making changes to the project by using an offline method called the Data Dictionary. It states that the Data Dictionary is a specifically formatted CSV file. A note mentions that a snapshot of the current Data Dictionary will be created automatically during the upload process. Below this, there is a section titled 'Need some help?' which provides links to a demonstration file and a tutorial video. The 'Steps for making project changes:' section lists four steps: 1.) Download the current Data Dictionary, 2.) Edit the Data Dictionary, 3.) Upload the Data Dictionary, and 4.) The changes will be made after the file is checked for errors. The bottom part of the screenshot shows the upload form with a red circle around the 'Choose File' button and a red arrow pointing to the 'Upload File' button. The form includes a dropdown for the date format (MM/DD/YYYY or YYYY-MM-DD) and a dropdown for the CSV delimiter (Comma (,)).

Project Home Project Setup Online Designer Data Dictionary Codebook

[VIDEO: How to use this page](#)

This module may be used for making changes to the project, such as adding new fields or modifying existing fields, by using an offline method called the Data Dictionary. The Data Dictionary is a specifically formatted CSV file within which you may construct your project fields and afterward upload the file here to commit the changes to your project.

Click the 'Browse' or 'Choose File' button below to select the file on your computer, and upload it by clicking the 'Upload File' button. Once your file has been uploaded, changes will NOT immediately be made but will be displayed and checked for errors to ensure that all the formatting in your Data Dictionary is correct before official changes are made to the project. **Snapshot note:** A snapshot of your project's current Data Dictionary will be created automatically during the Data Dictionary upload process before committing the new Data Dictionary. The snapshot can later be accessed and downloaded from the Project Revision History page.

Need some help?
If you wish to view an example of how your Data Dictionary may be formatted, you may download the [Data Dictionary demonstration file](#), or you may view the [Data Dictionary Tutorial Video \(10 min\)](#). For help setting up your Data Dictionary, you may also see the instructions listed on the [Help & FAQ](#).

Steps for making project changes:

- 1.) [Download the current Data Dictionary](#) - Also download with other delimiters: [Comma \(,\)](#), [Tab](#), [Semicolon \(;\)](#)
- 2.) Edit the Data Dictionary (see the [Help & FAQ](#) for help)
- 3.) Upload the Data Dictionary using the form below
- 4.) The changes will be made to the project after the Data Dictionary has been checked for errors

Upload your Data Dictionary file (CSV file format only)
Format for min/max validation values for date and datetime fields: MM/DD/YYYY or YYYY-MM-DD
CSV delimiter of data file: Comma (,)
Choose File no file selected
Upload File

Importing Data Dictionary

To import a data dictionary file into redcap, you can do the following:

1. go to the project setup tab for the project you want to import the structure into
2. select the data dictionary tab
3. select chose file under the title "Upload your Data Dictionary file:"
4. find the location of your data dictionary file, which should be a *.csv file
5. select the data dictionary file you want to import (*GaitDataDictionary_v1.csv*)
6. select upload file
7. select commit changes to import the data dictionary into your project
8. After pressing commit changes, you should see a message saying that the changes were made successfully.

[VIDEO: How to use this page](#)

✔ Your document was uploaded successfully and awaits your confirmation below.

- No errors or warnings were found in the document.
- The uploaded data dictionary **contains 179 fields**, which will replace the 179 fields that currently exist in the project (excluding 'Form Status' fields, which are automatically generated by REDCap).

Are you ready to commit the changes to the project from the uploaded Data Dictionary?
(Click the button below to submit the changes.)

Commit Changes [Cancel](#)

7

[VIDEO: How to use this page](#)

✔ Changes Made Successfully!

The field changes included in the uploaded Data Dictionary have been committed.

8

Visualize the forms and start personalizing your project

At this point, you have all the forms needed available.

If you go to add/edit records and for example add a mock subject, you will see your 4 forms (red rectangle).

By default, new projects will use the 'classic' data collection format, which is the best option if all data collection instruments will only need to be used once for each record in the project.

So, for example, If your study is cross-sectional, and you have only 1 gait condition associated to each participant (i.e. a 1-minute task at comfortable speed or daily life monitoring for 7 days) you do not need to add anything else, apart from other forms/tests you may want to collect.

However, if you have multiple gait tasks for the same participant, or a longitudinal study you need to make some adjustments as explained later.

Add / Edit Records

You may view an existing record/response by selecting it from the drop-down lists below. To create a new record/response, type in the text box below and hit Tab or Enter. To quickly find a record without using the drop-downs, the text box will auto-populate existing record names as you begin to type in it, allowing you to select it.

NOTICE: This project is currently in Development status. **Real data should NOT be entered** until the project has been moved to Production status.

Total records: 0

Choose an existing Participant Identifier: -- Select record --

Enter a new or existing Participant Identifier:

Data Search

Choose a field to search (excludes multiple choice fields): All fields

Search query
Begin typing to search the project data, then click an item in the list to navigate to that record.

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

Few important info on the 4 instruments you just imported

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

Basic Demographic
- Record ID
- Age at testing
- Years of post-secondary education
- Disease Duration (months from diagnosis)
- SOGI
- Race
- Ethnicity
- Descent

Basic demographics is the only form that you should not repeat, it contains information about your participant that are unlikely to change

Few important info on the 4 instruments you just imported

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

Demographics and Clinical
- Visit type
- Height (cm)
- Weight (kg)
- MDS-UPDRS Part I through IV
- H&Y
- FOG status: (Yes/No) + definition
- Falls (# past 6 months)
- PDQ-39 ^
- Levodopa Equivalent Dose ^^
- DBS status: (Yes/No) + DBS site
- Infusion Pump (Yes/No)
- MoCA
- Walk Independently (Yes/No)
- Walking Aid (Yes/No and Type)

Demographics and clinical contains several questions or forms that you may need to repeat based on the design of your study.

Visit type, we suggest to enter cross-sectional for one-time visit. For study with two or more visits, you can make this form repeatable. For example, then you can enter visit1, visit2 and so forth. For longitudinal studies over years, enter baseline, 6-months, 12months, 18months, and so forth. This way you can re-score MDS-UPDRS, FOG status, changes in medication and DBS.

Few important info on the 4 instruments you just imported

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

Location Specific Measures contains several questions or forms that you may need to repeat based on the design of your study and for example if you have both prescribed and unprescribed data collection for the same individual.

It starts by choosing the location and methods of gait testing and depending on the answer it will show up the pertinent next measures

Location Specific Measures

Editing existing Participant identifier 310. (Instance #1)

Event: Baseline

Participant identifier 310

Location and method of gait testing

* must provide value

Prescribed-Laboratory Prescribed-Clinical space Prescribed-home Unprescribed-home

Select one

Form Status

Complete? Incomplete

Save & Exit Form Save & Go To Next Form

- Cancel -

Prescribed (Laboratory/Clinic/Home)

- Medication Status at testing (On/Off)
- Walking Length (m)
- Walking Duration (s)
- Walking Turning Strategy
- DT details: type, performance seated (ST/DT)
- Walking Speed (i.e. comfortable/fast)
- # FoG Episodes Total
- # FOG observed (Straight Walking)
- # FOG observed (Turning)
- Tremor during gait testing
- Dyskinesia during gait testing
- Video Available (Yes/No)
- Mobile imaging (Yes/No)

Unprescribed: Daily Living

- Time(s) of Levodopa Doses
- # Days with Sensors
- # Hours per Day with Sensors
- Locations of Sensors
- Motor fluctuations in daily life (Yes/No)

Few important info on the 4 instruments you just imported

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

Consider repeating the **Location Specific Measures** form if for example you are collecting gait under single- and dual-task condition in the same session, and/or if any of the measures below needs repetition, i.e. Medication off vs on, walking at comfortable vs fast speed.

Prescribed (Laboratory/Clinic/Home)

- Medication Status at testing (On/Off)
- Walking Length (m)
- Walking Duration (s)
- Walking Turning Strategy
- DT details: type, performance seated (ST/DT)
- Walking Speed (i.e. comfortable/fast)
- # FoG Episodes Total
- # FOG observed (Straight Walking)
- # FOG observed (Turning)
- Tremor during gait testing
- Dyskinesia during gait testing
- Video Available (Yes/No)
- Mobile imaging (Yes/No)

Few important info on the 4 instruments you just imported

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

Gait Measures form contains all the recommended variables (mean and SD) that you need to report. Repeat the form if you have multiple conditions of gait tested and/or if you assess gait longitudinally in time.

It starts by asking whether your analysis is at the "Step" or "Stride" level and it then shows what you need to enter

Gait Measures

Editing existing Participant identifier 310. (Instance #1)

Event: Baseline

Participant identifier 310

Gait analysis at step or stride level?

* must provide value

Step

Stride

* Select one reset

Walking condition ST-Single Task DT-Dual Task reset

Few important info on the 4 ins

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

Example for "Stride" →

Gait Measures

Editing existing Participant identifier 310. (Instance #1)

Event: Baseline

Participant identifier 310

Gait analysis at step or stride level?
* must provide value

Step
 Stride

* Select one

Walking condition
 ST-Single Task
 DT-Dual Task

Amount of step/strides used for analysis

strides used for analysis in the laboratory/clinic

Minimum recommended

Gait speed (m/s)
* must provide value

Swing time asymmetry (%)
* must provide value

To calculate asymmetry please use this formula: $\text{abs}(\log_2(\min(\text{Right}, \text{Left})/\max(\text{Right}, \text{Left}))) * 100$

Stride length (m)
* must provide value

Stride time (s)
* must provide value

Stride time SD
* must provide value

Turning velocity (degrees/s)
* must provide value

steps/turn
* must provide value

Few important info on the 4 instruments you just imported

Data Collection Instrument	Status
Basic Demographics	<input type="radio"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input type="radio"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input type="radio"/>
Gait Measures	<input type="radio"/>

If available, also fill the additional recommended gait measures

If available	
Arm swing RoM (degrees)	<input type="text"/>
Arm swing RoM asymmetry (%)	<input type="text"/> <small>To calculate asymmetry please use this formula: $abs(\log_2(\min(\text{Right}, \text{Left})/\max(\text{Right}, \text{Left}))) * 100$</small>
Trunk coronal RoM (degrees)	<input type="text"/>
Pitch angle of the foot at heel-strike (degrees)	<input type="text"/>

Repeating instruments option in REDCap

REDCap has a feature to allow repeating instruments and events. This is very helpful if you have to collect multiple instances of the same data.

If some instruments need to be utilized repeatedly for a specific, finite number of times then **longitudinal data collection option** will likely be best. Additionally, the longitudinal format also allows one to utilize the scheduling module, if needed. If users are looking for instruments to be repeated without limit, the **repeating instruments option** seen within the “Enable optional modules and customizations” on the Project Setup page will be best.

Example: Your data collection includes gait single-task and gait dual-task collected in the same subject during a session in the laboratory while the participant is On their medication.

One way you can account for that is by using the repeating instruments option and make forms: *Location Specific Measures* and *Gait Measures* repeatable.

Repeating instruments option in REDCap

REDCap has a feature to allow repeating instruments and events. This is very helpful if you have to collect multiple instances of the same data.

If some instruments need to be utilized repeatedly, the **collection option** will likely be best. Additionally, if needed, the **optional module** seen within the “Enable optional modules” section.

Example: Your data collection includes gait analysis during a session in the laboratory while the participant is walking.

One way you can account for that is by using *Specific Measures* and *Gait Measures* repeatedly.

To do so, go to **Project Setup** → **Enable Repeating Instruments**

The screenshot shows the REDCap Project Setup interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Project Home, Project Setup (selected), Other Functionality, and Project Revision History. Below the tabs, the project status is 'Development' and 'Completed steps 0 of 7'. The main content is divided into three sections:

- Main project settings:** Includes 'Use surveys in this project?' (enabled), 'Use longitudinal data collection with defined events?' (enabled), and a 'Modify project title, purpose, etc.' button.
- Design your data collection instruments:** Includes links to 'Online Designer' and 'Data Dictionary', and a 'REDCap Instrument Library' link.
- Enable optional modules and customizations:** This section contains a list of optional modules with 'Enable' buttons and help icons. The 'Repeating instruments' option is highlighted with a red arrow and is currently enabled. Other options include 'Auto-numbering for records', 'Scheduling module (longitudinal only)', 'Randomization module', 'Designate an email field for communications', 'Dynamic Data Pull (DDP) from Research Data Warehouse', and 'Twilio SMS and Voice Call services for surveys and alerts'. There is also a 'Request Twilio' button.

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Repeating instruments option in REDCap

When clicking on Enable Repeating instruments a window pops-up to define which instrument should be repeated and whether a custom label should be associated to it.

The screenshot shows the REDCap Project Setup interface. The 'Enable optional modules and customizations' section is active, with 'Repeating instruments' selected. A modal window titled 'Repeating instruments' is open, providing instructions and a table to configure repeating instruments.

Repeating instruments

An excellent way to collect repeating data in REDCap is to use repeating instruments and/or repeating events. This is sometimes called one-to-many data collection. Some examples may include but are not limited to the following: data from multiple visits or observations, concomitant medications, adverse events, or repetitive surveys (daily, weekly, etc.).

Below you can specify a data collection instrument to be infinitely repeatable, which means that an instrument can be repeated over and over again (a different number of times for each record) even without enabling REDCap's longitudinal module. Once an instrument is set to repeat, you will see options on the Record Home Page to add another instance of the instrument for the currently selected record. All instances of a repeating instrument will then be displayed as a table near the bottom of the Record Home Page, thus allowing viewing of the instances and easy navigation within them.

Repeat this instrument?	Instrument name	Custom label for repeating instruments (optional) <small>Example: [visit_date], [weight] kg</small>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Basic Demographics	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Demographics And Clinical	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Location Specific Measures	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gait Measures	<input type="text"/>

Save Cancel

Repeating instruments option in REDCap

When clicking on Enable Repeating instruments a window pops-up to define which instrument should be repeated and whether a custom label should be associated to it.

For the example of single- and dual-task, you should click on repeating for **Location Specific Measures** and **Gait Measures** and specify as label *dual_task_presence*

After that, press SAVE and the page will reload.

Repeat this instrument?	Instrument name	Custom label for repeating instruments (optional) Example: [visit_date], [weight] kg
<input type="checkbox"/>	Basic Demographics	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	Demographics And Clinical	<input type="text"/>
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Location Specific Measures	[dual_task_presence]
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Gait Measures	[dual_task_presence]

Save

Cancel

Repeating instruments option in REDCap

When clicking on Enable Repeating instruments a window pops-up to define which instrument should be repeated and whether a custom label should be associated to it.

For the example of single- and dual-task, you should click on repeating for **Location Specific Measures** and **Gait Measures** and specify as label `dual_task_presence`

After that, press SAVE and the page will reload. Now **Repeating Instrument** is in green and you can modify further if needed.

The screenshot shows the REDCap Project Setup interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Project Home, Project Setup, Other Functionality, and Project Revision History. Below the tabs, the project status is 'Development' and 'Completed steps 0 of 7'. The main content is divided into three sections:

- Main project settings:** Includes options to 'Enable Use surveys in this project?' and 'Enable Use longitudinal data collection with defined events?'. A 'Modify project title, purpose, etc.' button is also present.
- Design your data collection instruments:** Provides instructions on adding or editing fields, with links to 'Online Designer' and 'Data Dictionary'. It also includes a 'Check For Identifiers' link and various tool icons like Smart Variables, Piping, Action Tags, Field Embedding, and Special Functions.
- Enable optional modules and customizations:** This section is highlighted with a green arrow. It lists several modules that can be enabled or disabled, including 'Repeating instruments' (which is currently checked and highlighted in green), 'Auto-numbering for records', 'Scheduling module (longitudinal only)', 'Randomization module', 'Designate an email field for communications', 'Dynamic Data Pull (DDP) from Research Data Warehouse', and 'Twilio SMS and Voice Call services for surveys and alerts'. A 'Request Twilio' button is also visible.

Longitudinal data collection option in REDCap

Another way of setting-up your study, ideal if you have multiple, defined visits, is to use the **longitudinal data collection option**. **Example**, if you are measuring gait in participants at baseline and at 12-month the Longitudinal data collection option will serve you best.

To enable Longitudinal Data Collection in a REDCap project requires enabling the longitudinal data collection from the Project Setup page, then defining events and designating instruments per event.

Follow these steps to effectively enable longitudinal data collection in your project:

1. From the **Project Setup Page**, click "Enable" next to **Use longitudinal data collection with defined events?**
2. The screen will refresh and the **Use longitudinal data collection with defined events?** text will turn green
3. A new box on the **Project Setup** page will appear called **Define your events and designate instruments for them**.

Longitudinal data collection option in REDCap

- To define events for the project, click the **"Define My Events"** button under Define your events and designate instruments for them
- Longitudinal projects initially have one arm and one event. To customize event names (like "Event 1") click the pencil icon, edit the Event Label and Custom Event Label (optional), and then save. To add additional events within this Arm, type in a new event label (and custom label if desired) then click "Add new event". (Note: Users may repeat this process as many times as needed.)
- Once events are defined, instruments must be designated per event. To designate instruments per event, click on the "Designate Instruments for My Events" button which can be found on both the Project Setup Page and the Define My Events page.

	Event # [event-number]	Event Label [event-label]	Custom Event Label (optional)	Unique event name (auto-generated) [event-name]	Event ID (auto-generated, unchangeable) [event-id]
	1	Baseline		baseline_arm_1	139766
	2	12-month		12month_arm_1	139846

 [VIDEO: How to define events \(5 min\)](#)

This application allows you to define 'events' for your project that allow for the **utilization of data collection forms multiple times for any given project record** (often used when collecting longitudinal data). An 'event' may be a temporal event in the course of your project, such as a participant visit or a task to be performed. After events have been defined, you will need to designate the data collection instruments that you wish to utilize for any or all events, thus allowing you to use a form for multiple events for the same project record. You may **group your events into 'arms'**, in which you may have one or more arms/groups for your project. Each arm can have as many events as you wish. You may use the table below to create new events and/or arms, or modify existing ones. (One arm and one event will be initially defined as the default for all projects.)

STEP #1:

To add new events below, provide an **Event Name** for that event, and then click the *Add new event*. Once events have been added, you can easily change their order by dragging and dropping the event using the up-down arrow icon on the far left for a given row in the table.

Longitudinal data collection option in REDCap

- Click the "Begin Editing" button
- Add the forms you need to repeat for the 12-month event, for example, see below
- Save

Data Collection Instrument	Baseline (1)	12-month (2)
Basic Demographics	✓	
Demographics And Clinical	✓	
Location Specific Measures	✓	
Gait Measures	✓	

Data Collection Instrument	Event 1 (1)	12-month (2)
Basic Demographics	✓	<input type="checkbox"/>
Demographics And Clinical	✓	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Location Specific Measures	✓	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Gait Measures	✓	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Data Collection Instrument	Baseline (1)	12-month (2)
Basic Demographics	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Demographics And Clinical	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Location Specific Measures	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Gait Measures	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Good to know

- We hope this tutorial and the data dictionary are helpful to you!
- We made this available for the REDCap users, but likely with some edits you can use or implement the data dictionary in other electronic data capture systems.
- **KEEP IN MIND:** the way you design your study influences your data export, so make sure that the data export looks similar to the proposed ones in the .csv examples we provide.
- REDCap provides a lot of great resources that you can use to further personalize your study.